

Solving the part transportation problem from suppliers to factories in the automotive industry

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Abstract

Planning the transportation of car parts from suppliers to assembly plants is a critical issue for automotive industries, which rely on complex supply chains. Over a planning horizon of several weeks, two decisions have to be made. First, how to assign parts to trucks, taking into account early and late delivery dates for parts and the planned truck schedule. Next, how to load the parts onto the trucks, a complex packing problem that must take into account multiple practical constraints, such as weight distribution, stability, orientation, and fragility. We follow a decomposition strategy, solving the first assignment problem approximately using an integer linear model, and developing a metaheuristic algorithm for the packing phase. We then study several strategies for combining these two elements in a matheuristic framework. Computational results on a set of instances provided by a major automotive manufacturer show that the proposed algorithm improves on the best published results, producing many new best solutions.

keyword: container loading optimization heuristic algorithm

1 Introduction

The automotive industry is composed of a complex set of companies involved in designing, manufacturing, and marketing motor vehicles. A car has several thousand parts, and nowadays car factories do not make most, if any, of them. Instead, they rely on a complex network of suppliers from whom they receive individual parts or sub-assemblies. This organization creates major logistics problems. For European car plants, trucks and trains are used for transport across Europe, and containers and ships are used for intercontinental transport. In the case of Renault, their supply chain includes 40 factories in 17 countries and 1500 suppliers (Nguyen et al., 2022). Every week, 6000 trucks move parts from suppliers to plants. The problem has important economic implications: Renault’s annual transportation budget is several hundred million euros. But it also has environmental implications: reducing the number of trucks on the roads will reduce congestion and emissions, so it can be embedded in the general trend towards sustainable supply chains (Nieuwenhuis et al., 2012; Siems et al., 2021).

In 2015, Renault, together with ESICUP, the EURO Working Group in Cutting and Packing, proposed a challenge for minimizing the number of trucks and containers needed to send parts between the group’s factories. No routing was involved, but rather point-to-point transportation, so the problem was basically a container loading problem with additional constraints. Many research teams around the world developed algorithms and some of them have been published (Correcher et al., 2017; Toffolo et al., 2017).

More recently, in 2022, Renault launched a new challenge, together with ROADEF (the French Operational Research Society), proposing these large-scale logistics problems for the transportation of parts from suppliers to factories. Besides the truck loading, two new elements have been added. Some trucks can pick up parts from several suppliers, following a predefined route, which imposes a last-in-first-out constraint on the packing process. There is also a temporal planning of shipments with associated storage costs. Thus, the new problem involves not only routing but also inventory management.

This paper addresses the problem proposed in this recent Renault challenge and proposes several matheuristic strategies to obtain high-quality solutions within the time limits set by the company. In this problem, the planning of shipments from a set of suppliers to a factory over a horizon of several weeks must be determined. For each part provided by each supplier, the dates on which the factory will require it and the quantities are known. The part may arrive just at the time it is needed or it may arrive early, within a given interval, usually ranging from 1 to 5 days, but in this case it incurs a daily inventory cost. Parts are transported by trucks. Renault contracts a set of trucks on an annual schedule, the “planned trucks”, defined by the time they arrive at the factory, the types of parts they can carry, and the subset of suppliers they visit. Some trucks go directly from one supplier to the factory, but others have a predefined route that visits several suppliers. If the planned trucks are not enough to transport all required parts, “extra” trucks can be used, although at a higher cost. The factory must receive all the required parts at their predefined intervals while minimizing the total cost, which includes the cost of trucks and the inventory costs. Inventory costs are very important for Renault, as they can amount to several hundred million euros, so parts should be delivered as late as possible, while at the same time minimizing the cost of the trucks. A large instance can have up to 260,000 parts and 5,000 planned trucks.

As the instances to be solved are usually very large, we have opted for a decomposition strategy, separating the two decisions to be made for each part to be shipped, first when and in which truck to ship it and then in which position in the truck it is loaded. The first phase is an assignment problem that we solve approximately using an integer linear model that does not take into account the position of parts in the truck. The second phase is a container loading problem, and we have developed a metaheuristic algorithm, taking into account all the specificities of the Renault loading process: orientation, fragility, multidrop, stability, and weight distribution. To combine these two elements we have studied several matheuristic strategies, different ways of passing information between them. These strategies have been tested on a set of instances provided by Renault, many of them very large, and the results show that the best strategy outperforms the best reported proposals, yielding many new best solutions.

The main contributions of the paper are:

- Several strategies for decomposing the original problem into smaller subproblems based on truck routes and arrival times, the types of parts each truck can carry, and the early and late delivery dates of the parts.
- An integer linear model for assigning parts to trucks, considering transportation and inventory costs and the weight and volume of the parts.
- A metaheuristic algorithm that, given a list of parts and a truck, produces a packing that maximizes the volume of the packed parts, considering practical constraints: orientation, fragility, multidrop, static and dynamic stability, and weight distribution constraints.
- Several matheuristic strategies for combining the two elements that compose the problem. Each strategy is defined by how the integer linear model is solved and what information from the model solution is passed to the packing algorithm.
- Many new best solutions over the set of instances provided by Renault. Overall, the proposed algorithm improves on the best results reported for the challenge.

The remainder of the paper is as follows. The relevant literature for the problem studied in this work is reviewed in Section 2. Section 3 describes the problem with all its elements and constraints. The instance sets provided by Renault are presented and analyzed in Section 4. The decomposition strategies and their effects appear in Section 5. In Section 6, the integer linear assignment model is presented, while Section 7 contains the packing algorithm. The matheuristic strategies are discussed in Section 8. Finally, we show the results of the computational study in Section 9, and the conclusions derived in Section 10.

2 Literature review

Multi-Container Loading Problems (MCLPs), like many other packing problems, have geometric constraints to prevent items from overlapping and exceeding the container dimensions. However, container loading problems have many other constraints, because containers (or trucks) move the items, and therefore physical characteristics of both containers and items as well as their interaction must be taken into account to provide solutions that are useful in practice. A list of 12 realistic constraints was already introduced by Bischoff and Ratcliff (1995), but twenty years later, the study by Bortfeldt and Wäscher (2013) found that very few of the published papers had considered several of these constraints simultaneously. However, the situation has improved recently. Surveys by Pollaris et al. (2015) on routing and packing problems and Neuenfeldt Júnior et al. (2022) on the related strip packing problem show a growing interest in including such constraints, especially those that are critical to ensure safe transportation of cargo, such as those concerning weight distribution and stability. In this review, we will focus on the constraints relevant to the Renault logistics problem.

Among the item-related constraints, a very common constraint concerns the orientation of the items. Each item has six possible orientations and although sometimes the orientation is not restricted, it is very common that only one vertical orientation is allowed, permitting a 90° rotation in the horizontal plane (the "This side up" constraint) as in Çalık et al. (2023). Sometimes, items cannot be rotated at all (Alonso et al., 2019, 2022). In the Renault problem, the vertical dimension is fixed and only horizontal rotations are allowed, although for some parts the orientation is fixed and no rotation is permitted.

Load-bearing constraints (also known as stacking constraints) control how items can be placed on top of each other. Sometimes, these constraints are implemented by dividing items into two categories, fragile and non-fragile, and requiring either that no non-fragile item can be on top of a fragile one, although fragile items can be stacked on top of each other (Fuellerer et al., 2010), or that no item can be placed above a fragile item (Junqueira et al., 2012a). An alternative approach considers a limit on the pressure an item can withstand from items placed above it (Junqueira et al., 2012a; Alonso et al., 2014). In the Renault case, there are two types of constraints. On the one hand, items can only be stacked if they have the same dimensions and the same stackability code. On the other hand, for some items there is a maximum number of items that can be placed on top and there may also be limits on the total weight of the items stacked above the bottom item and on the density of a stack.

Among the cargo-related conditions, a first group of constraints concerns the weight of the items loaded in the container. Beyond the basic constraint limiting the total weight the container can carry, which is included in most studies, the critical issue is the weight distribution, measured as the force exerted on the axles of the truck and the position of the centre of gravity. Excesses over the axle weight limits represent a risk to traffic safety and can cause damage to the road, especially on bridges. They are therefore strictly controlled and violations are severely punished. Many countries are implementing Weight-In-Motion systems, which monitor axle weight violations while driving (Stone, 2024).

Realistic load balance methods based on axle weight restrictions appear in several recent CLP studies (Lim et al., 2013; Pollaris et al., 2016; Alonso et al., 2017, 2022), adapting the calculation to the type of truck being considered. Other studies focus on the position of the centre of gravity of the load, requiring it to be near the geometric centre of the truck, although with some tolerances (Alonso et al., 2019; Neuenfeldt Júnior et al., 2022). Ramos et al. (2018) go further and develop load distribution diagrams, vehicle-specific diagrams that show the admissible total weight of the cargo as a function of the position of its centre of gravity. For this challenge, Renault provided the equations for calculating the weight on the two axles of the trucks they use, as well as the weight limits.

The other main condition in truck transportation is the stability of the cargo. Static stability refers to the stability of the items while being loaded or unloaded when the truck is not moving. Dynamic stability refers to preventing the items from being displaced and damaged when the truck is moving, subject to accelerations, braking, and turns.

Static stability has usually been ensured by imposing full base support on the items, so that their base is supported from below on the truck floor or on other items, or partial support, when only a certain percentage of the base must be supported from below (Fanslau and Bortfeldt, 2010; Junqueira et al., 2012a). However, Ramos et al. (2016) have demonstrated that this approach is too restrictive and have developed a more efficient approach, based on static mechanical equilibrium conditions applied to rigid bodies. In Renault's

case, static stability is always ensured because every item in a stack has the same base dimension as the item below it, so it is fully supported.

Dynamic stability, ensuring that items will not move when the truck is moving, has been less studied. Ramos et al. (2015) have proposed new metrics, extending the ideas of Bischoff and Ratcliff (1995). Basically, they measure whether there is empty space between items that would allow displacements when the truck accelerates, brakes, or turns. When the cargo is loaded on pallets, instead of individual boxes, dynamic stability is enforced by not allowing gaps between them (Pollaris et al., 2016; Alonso et al., 2022) and limiting the difference in height of adjacent pallets (Alonso et al., 2017). Çalık et al. (2023) ensure stability by adding air cushions to fill the empty spaces between pallets. At Renault, dynamic stability is considered by forcing each stack to be adjacent to another stack to its left or to the front of the truck.

Multidrop constraints arise when a truck visits several customers to deliver or pick up items. The placement of the items in the truck must respect the order in which the customers are visited to ensure that items for a customer being served can be unloaded from the vehicle without moving items for other customers to be served later. Multidrop constraints are always considered in vehicle routing problems with loading constraints, but they also appear in packing problems in which the route visiting several customers is given.

The first paper that considered multidrop situations was that of Bischoff and Ratcliff (1995). Since then, other studies have followed proposing various ways of dealing with these constraints (see Alvarez et al. (2015) for a review). Multidrop constraints are nowadays included in integer linear models (Junqueira et al., 2012a; de Queiroz and Miyazawa, 2013; Pollaris et al., 2016; Alonso et al., 2022; Çalık et al., 2023), as well as in metaheuristic algorithms (Alvarez et al., 2015; Iori et al., 2020). In a recent paper, Bonet Filella et al. (2023) propose treating multidrop constraints as soft constraints whose violation is penalized and show that this more flexible approach can lead to much higher objective value solutions compared to the direct application of hard unloading constraints. In the Renault problem, there is a triple ordering, concerning the way items are loaded at the suppliers and unloaded at the plant. Items must be placed from the front to the rear of the truck, following first the supplier pickup order, then the order of loading at the supplier’s docks, and finally the order of unloading at the plant’s docks. There is also a parameter indicating whether items from different suppliers can be placed in the same stack.

The second main characteristic of the problem, that of including early and late delivery dates for the products and, hence, inventory costs, has not usually been considered in combined routing and packing problems. However, in related cutting and packing problems, there are several studies in which the pieces to be cut have due dates and in the objective function tardiness is considered (Braga et al., 2016; Polyakovskiy and M’Hallah, 2018). Among the routing problems, the Inventory Routing Problem (IRP) combines routing and inventory decisions. According to Bertazzi and Speranza (2013), in the IRP the daily consumption of a product by a set of customers is known and the quantities to be delivered daily have to be determined. The problem, then, is deciding what quantity to send to each customer and organizing the routes, with the goal of minimizing total inventory and routing costs. Many different approaches have been studied for this problem, from integer linear models (Archetti et al., 2014), branch and bound, and branch and cut algorithms (Avella et al., 2018) to metaheuristics (Alvarez et al., 2018) and mathheuristics (Archetti et al., 2021). Nevertheless, although it is related, the problem considered here is not properly an inventory routing problem, because there are many products to be sent, the truck routes are fixed, and the trucks have a fixed arrival time at the plant.

There is only one paper on the Renault problem proposed in the challenge, recently published by Schulte and Wetzel (2025). They use a decomposition in two phases, one for assignment and one for packing, similar to the approach developed in our study, but the models and heuristic algorithms they propose for the two phases are very different, as well as the way they combine the two phases. The computational study in Section 9 includes a comparison with the results of their algorithm.

3 Description of the problem

In this section we will formally describe the elements of the problem and introduce the notation necessary for the development of models and algorithms. Suppliers place the parts corresponding to each product in boxes to be loaded into trucks. Although determining the best box for each product is an interesting optimization problem in itself (Knoll et al., 2019; Cildoz et al., 2024), in this case the boxes have already been determined for each product. Following the usual terminology in packing problems, the boxes to be transported will be

referred to as items. A complete technical description of the problem can be found in Nguyen et al. (2022). Although in the description of the problem they consider a set of plants to which the items are shipped, in all instances of this challenge there is a unique plant, thus defining the problem as one plant and its suppliers. Therefore, we have simplified the problem description by considering a single plant.

3.1 Items

An item i is a box containing a part of type IR_i , with dimensions (IL_i, IW_i, IH_i) , volume IV_i , and weight IM_i . By convention, the length is larger than or equal to the width. Each item also has a stackability code IS_i , so that only items with the same stackability code can be put into the same stack, and a maximal stackability ISM_i , representing the maximal number of items i in a stack.

Items can only be rotated in the horizontal dimension. An item can be oriented lengthwise (with its length parallel to the truck length) or widthwise (with its length parallel to the truck width). An item i can have a forced orientation IO_i . In this case, all items in its stack must have the same orientation.

Item i must be delivered to the plant within a time window $[IDE_i, IDL_i]$, where IDE_i is the earliest arrival time and IDL_i the latest. If the item is delivered before IDL_i , it incurs a daily inventory cost IC_i . The item is produced by a supplier IU_i , loaded at supplier dock IK_i and unloaded at plant dock IG_i .

3.2 Trucks

A planned truck t has dimensions (TL_t, TW_t, TH_t) , volume TV_t , maximum loading weight TM_t^m , and a fixed cost TC_t , regardless of the items carried.

A truck t visits a set of suppliers TU_t in a given order and arrives at the plant at time TDA_t . As the truck may not stop at all docks of the plant, it may not be able to transport all types of items, but only a subset TR_t .

If there are not enough planned trucks to deliver all items on time, extra trucks can be used. An extra truck t_e is defined from a planned truck t , from which it inherits all its characteristics, although at a higher cost $TC_{t_e} = (1 + \alpha^E)TC_t$, where α^E is a cost parameter.

3.3 Stacks

The items loaded into a truck are piled up in stacks, subject to certain conditions. All items in a stack must have the same base dimensions, the same orientation, and the same stackability code. All stacks packed in truck t must have a maximum density TEM_t . There is a maximum total weight $TMM_t\gamma$ for the items packed above the bottom item of type γ in any stack loaded for each item i of a stack s , the number of items of s must not exceed ISM_i on truck t . For each item i of a stack s , the number of items of s must not exceed ISM_i .

The stack weight is the sum of the weights of the items composing it, and the stack height is the sum of their heights, although in some cases an item i , due to its packaging, may be partially nested into the item below it, so a nesting height $I\hat{H}_i$ must be subtracted from the sum of heights.

3.4 Objective

The objective is to minimize the total cost, which is a sum of the transportation and inventory costs. The transportation cost is the cost of the planned and extra trucks and depends only on the number of trucks, irrespective of the items loaded in them. The inventory cost corresponds to the early delivery of items, calculated as the inventory cost of the item multiplied by the number of days between the delivery date and the latest arrival time. The relative weights of the two cost components are controlled by parameters α^T and α^I .

3.5 Constraints

There are four sets of constraints:

1. Item constraints

- All items must be packed in stacks, which must be loaded into planned or extra trucks.
- An item i can be loaded into a truck t if and only if:
 - truck t can pick up the item type IR_i
 - truck t visits supplier IR_i
 - truck t arrives at the plant within the item’s time window: $IDE_i \leq TDA_t \leq IDL_i$

2. Stack constraints

- All items in a stack must have the same base dimensions and the same supplier, supplier dock, and stackability code.
- Each truck t has a TF_t (yes/no) flag. If $TF_t = no$, all items in a stack must share the same plant dock. If $TF_t = yes$, a stack can contain items from two plant docks with consecutive loading orders. In this case, for every stackability code present among the items in the truck, only one stack with this stackability code can contain items from two plant docks.
- If one item i in a stack has a forced orientation IO_i , then all the items in the stack must share the same orientation.
- The total weight of the items packed in a stack above the bottom item cannot exceed $TMM_t\gamma$, where γ is the type of the bottom item.
- For each item i in a stack, the number of items in the stack must not exceed ISM_i , a maximum stackability parameter associated with i .
- The density of a stack cannot exceed the maximum stack density defined for the truck t in which the stack is loaded, TEM_t .

3. Placement constraints

- The placement of a stack into a truck must not exceed the truck’s dimensions.
- The stacks packed into a truck cannot overlap.
- Each stack must be adjacent to another stack to its left or to the front of the truck.
- Stacks must be placed from the front to the rear of the truck, according to the increasing order of collection from the suppliers. Among stacks from the same supplier, stacks must be placed in increasing order in the supplier’s loading dock. Among stacks from the same supplier and supplier’s dock, stacks must be placed in increasing order of loading at the plant’s dock.

4. Weight constraints

- The total weight of the stacks packed in a truck must not exceed the truck’s maximum loading weight TM_i^m .
- The weights on the middle and rear axle of a truck must not exceed the maximum weight authorized for these axles, EM_{mm} and EM_{mr} . Details of the calculation of the weights on the axles as proposed by Renault can be found in Nguyen et al. (2022).

These constraints must be met whenever the truck is on the road. If a truck goes first to pick up items from supplier A and then from supplier B, the constraints must be satisfied first with the items from supplier A and then with the items from suppliers A and B.

4 Benchmarks

Several sets of instances were made available during the phases of the challenge: set A for the initial sprint phase, set B for the qualification phase, and set C for the final phase. In the final evaluation of the algorithms, an unknown set X was also used and made available afterwards. The main characteristics of the instances in each set are summarized in Table 1, which shows for each set the number of instances and the maximum, average, and minimum number of items and trucks. A graphical comparison of the four sets is shown in

Table 1: Comparing the four sets of instances

Set	Instances	Items			Trucks		
		Maximum	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Minimum
A	30	19114	9590	953	1770	970	157
B	40	21063	8506	203	2078	951	29
C	50	65274	21644	684	6774	2371	66
X	105	50750	18765	123	5831	1774	19

Figure 1: Comparing the sizes of instances in the four sets of instances

Figure 1. It can be observed that the instances in sets C and X tend to be larger than those in sets A and B, involving in some cases tens of thousands of items and several thousand trucks.

Sets C and X were used for the final evaluation and the results obtained by the competing teams are public. The challenge website has also published new results for these two sets, extending the initial time limits. Therefore, we will use these two sets to compare the results of our algorithms with the best published results.

For each instance, the information is contained in three Excel files. The *input_items* file contains all the information about the items to be transported, as described in Section 3. These items define the problem to be solved. The *input_trucks* file contains information about the planned trucks, but is not synchronized with the *input_items* file. There may be trucks visiting suppliers that are not in the items file, so they are not part of the problem, and there may be trucks that can only transport product types that are not in the items file. Therefore, these trucks can be removed, leaving only those that can carry the problem items.

One of the objectives of reading and processing the data is to directly link the items and the trucks, since in the Excel files they are linked by supplier and type of product. The models and algorithms we have developed require, for each truck, the list of suppliers it visits and in what order, and for each of these suppliers, the list of items that can be transported in the truck, sorted by supplier dock and plant dock. The items are also ordered by inventory cost, with priority given to those with higher costs.

The third file, the *input_parameters* file, is an auxiliary file containing four parameters, the weights of the inventory and transportation costs, α^T and α^I , the incremental cost of the extra trucks, α^E , and the time limit set for the instance. Among the 155 instances of the sets C and X, in 63 $\alpha^T = \alpha^I = 1$, in 46 $\alpha^T = 1$ and $\alpha^I = 5$, and in 46 $\alpha^T = 5$ and $\alpha^I = 1$. The balance between transportation and inventory costs varies in each case, so algorithms must take this information into account in order to obtain minimum cost solutions.

5 Decomposing the problem into independent subproblems

In this section we will describe several ways of decomposing the original problem into subproblems that can be solved independently, thus reducing the size of the problem to which models and algorithms are applied.

5.1 A decomposition based on truck routes

Looking at the suppliers that each truck visits, some interesting structures can be found. There are suppliers for which a set of trucks is assigned and these trucks make a point-to-point transportation from the supplier to the plant, without visiting any other supplier. In this case, the problem defined by the items and trucks involved in this supplier-plant connection can be solved independently from the problem of transporting all other items from the rest of the suppliers. There are other situations involving two suppliers, A and B, such that there is a set of trucks with routes A-B-P (plant), B-A-P, A-P, B-P, and there is no truck that visits A or B and also visits other suppliers. In this case, the problem defined by the items to be shipped from A and B and all trucks assigned to them form an independent problem. Note that the trucks only visiting A or visiting B are also included, because the decision on the items shipped on those trucks is influenced by the decisions on the items sent on the trucks that visit both suppliers.

There are other similar situations involving more than two suppliers, but defined in the same way, a set of suppliers for which there is a set of trucks visiting a subset of these suppliers but no truck visiting some suppliers in this set and other suppliers outside the set.

This partition of the set of suppliers into disjoint subsets corresponds mathematically to determining the connected components in a graph. We define a graph $G = (V, E)$ whose vertex set V is the set of suppliers and an edge $e = (s, s')$ exists in E if there is at least one truck visiting s and s' . The connected components in this graph G can be obtained using the Kosaraju-Sharir algorithm (Sharir, 1981) and these components correspond to subsets of suppliers defining independent subproblems.

5.2 A decomposition based on product types and delivery dates

Each of the subproblems created in the previous decomposition is composed of a set of suppliers, their items to be shipped and the set of trucks exclusively serving them. Within this subproblem other decompositions are sometimes possible. As commented in the problem description, when building the list of items each truck can carry, an item is included if its delivery interval contains the truck's arrival time and its product type can be carried by the truck. Not all trucks can carry all product types because each product type is unloaded at a specific plant dock and the truck's route may not include this dock. Therefore, it may happen that a subset of trucks can only carry a subset of items and none of the other trucks can carry any of these items. In this case, a subproblem with this subset of trucks and the corresponding items can be solved independently. This type of decomposition can be determined by obtaining the connected components in a graph whose vertices are the trucks and in which there is an edge between two vertices if they have at least one item in common.

5.3 Effect of these decompositions on the test instances

The effect of applying these decompositions to the instances of sets C and X is shown in Table 2. The table has two parts. The upper part summarizes the number of components per instance, showing the maximum, minimum, average, and median. This number varies greatly between instances, ranging from 3 to 328 in set C and from 1 to 572 in set X. As the objective of the decomposition is to solve smaller subproblems, the second part of the table shows how big the largest component is in each instance, measured as the number of items. Again, the data show a great deal of variability. There are some cases in which the largest component is very large, with up to ten thousand items, but there are many others in which the largest component is rather small, compared to the size of the original problem, and the decompositions effectively produced many small subproblems. Figure 2 shows the two aspects, number of components and maximum size, for the instances of set X. Figure 3 compares for each instance the size of the original problem, in green, and that of its largest component, in orange. It can be observed that in many cases the size reduction is drastic, especially for the largest instances.

Table 2: Number of components and size of largest component

Set	Number of components			
	Maximum	Minimum	Average	Median
C	328	3	103	102
X	572	1	197	135
Set	Largest component			
	Maximum	Minimum	Average	Median
C	13806	285	3285	3414
X	9123	109	2624	1931

Figure 2: Number of components and largest component in set X

5.4 A further time-based decomposition

If any of the components obtained by the decompositions described above is still too large to be solved efficiently by the algorithms that will be described in the next sections, a third heuristic decomposition can be applied. Along the planning horizon (H_s, H_e) a point T is chosen and the problem is decomposed into two subproblems, one with interval (H_s, T) and one with (T, H_e) . Each truck t is assigned to the interval in which its arrival time, TDA_t , falls. Each item i is assigned to the subproblem in which its latest arrival time, IDL_i , falls. This decomposition loses some possible assignments of the items whose $IDE_i < T$ and $IDL_i > T$, because their interval reduces to (T, IDL_i) , but its use can significantly reduce solution times.

6 An integer linear model for assigning items to trucks

The transportation problem, involving thousands of items and trucks, can be seen as composed of two decisions: determine which items go in each truck and decide how to pack the items into the truck. We have separated these two decisions and developed a two-phase algorithmic scheme. In this section, we describe the integer model we use to assign items to trucks. In the next section, we will describe the packing algorithm for the second phase, and then we will discuss possible ways of combining these two elements into a matheuristic algorithm for the original problem.

We have developed an integer linear problem to assign items to trucks, considering only the due dates, weight, and volume of items and trucks, that is, constraints related to the number of items of each part type assigned to each truck. Constraints concerning the weight on the axles or the relative positions of items from different suppliers would require variables defining the positions of the items in the truck. Although this can be done, as in Junqueira et al. (2012b) and Kurpel et al. (2020), the model could not handle the large instances to be solved.

In addition to the notation introduced in Section 3, for each truck t we define I_t as the set of item types

Figure 3: Comparing the total number of items and the items of the largest component in set X

i that can be loaded in this truck. For each planned truck $t \in T$, we create as many extra trucks as needed to ensure that all the items that can be loaded in the truck, I_t , can fit by weight and volume in the planned truck plus its cloned extra trucks. We denote the set of extra trucks by T' . The variables are:

x_{it} = number of items of type i in truck t , $t \in T \cup T'$

$$z_t = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if truck } t \text{ is used, } j \in T \cup T' \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The model is:

$$\text{Minimize } \alpha^T \sum_{t \in T \cup T'} TC_t z_t + \alpha^I \sum_{t \in T \cup T'} \sum_{i \in I_t} IC_i (IDL_i - TDA_t) x_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{t \in T \cup T'} x_{it} = n_i \quad \forall i \in I \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I_t} IV_i x_{it} \leq TV_t z_t \quad \forall t \in T \cup T' \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I_t} IM_i x_{it} \leq TM_t^m z_t \quad \forall t \in T \cup T' \quad (4)$$

$$x_{it} \in \{0, \dots, n_i\} \quad j \in T \cup T', i \in I_t \quad (5)$$

$$z_t \in \{0, 1\} \quad j \in T \cup T' \quad (6)$$

The objective function (1) minimizes the sum of the cost of trucks, planned and extra, and the inventory cost, each term multiplied by its weight, α^T or α^I . Constraints (2) ensure that all the items are shipped. Constraints (3) and (4) limit the volume and weight of the items assigned to each truck to the volume and maximum weight of the truck. With these constraints, the model systematically produces item assignments that cannot be packed by the loading algorithm described in the next section, because the model does not take into account many packing requirements, such as the supplier and loading dock order and the rules for building stacks, and mainly because it is a one-dimensional approximation to a three-dimensional packing problem. One way of bringing the solution of the model closer to the packing phase is to use as TV_t and TM_t^m the values obtained by applying a version of the loading algorithm to each truck and the list of items that could be loaded in this truck. Using the volume and weight of this heuristic solution in constraints (3) and (4) results in allocations of items to trucks much closer to what the loading algorithm would be able to load.

7 A heuristic algorithm for packing items into trucks

We have developed a multistart randomized packing algorithm that runs for a given number of iterations. At each iteration, a constructive algorithm with several random elements constructs a complete solution for a truck and its associated list of items, and the solution with the largest packed volume is chosen.

7.1 A deterministic constructive algorithm

The constructive algorithm has the following steps:

Step 0. Initialization

The items must be ordered by supplier, supplier loading dock, and plant dock as imposed by the placement constraints. If there are items that cannot be packed into any other truck, we mark them as mandatory and they occupy the first positions in their supplier-supplier loading dock-plant dock subgroup. If no mandatory items have been identified according to this criterion, we consider as mandatory all those items for which the truck's arrival time is their early delivery time, so they can be loaded into other trucks arriving on the same day but not into those arriving on previous days.

The items in each subgroup are finally sorted according to an item-related criterion, such as volume, weight, width, or inventory cost.

Step 1. Selecting the position for the next stack

Consider the truck floor as a rectangle (L, W) in the plane, with its length on the x -axis and its width on the y -axis, and with the origin at its bottom left corner.

We keep a list of vertical segments (x, y_1, y_2) , where x is the horizontal position and y_1 and y_2 define the vertical start and end points. The space to the right of each vertical segment is empty and can be used to place the next stack. Initially, this list contains only the segment $(0, 0, W)$ and every time a new stack is placed it is updated, adding new segments, merging them with other segments if they are vertically contiguous and have the same horizontal component, and removing them if no remaining items from the supplier being loaded can fit, in a similar way to the algorithms for solving the strip packing problem (Allen et al., 2011; Wei et al., 2011).

In this step, the segment with the smallest x is chosen. If there is a tie, the narrowest segment is selected.

Step 2. Selecting the item to be the base of the new stack

Select the first item in the list of the supplier being loaded that fits in the space defined by the selected segment, according to its dimensions in the allowed orientations and its weight.

Step 3. Selecting the orientation of the item

If the orientation is not fixed, we calculate for the two orientations the quotient between the width of the segment and the dimension of the item in that orientation. The one with the lower fractional part is chosen. However, if the difference between these fractional parts is small, less than 0.05, the orientation is chosen at random.

Step 4. Selecting the position of the item

If the width of the item is less than the width of the segment, the vertical position of the item must be decided. The position closest to one side of the truck is chosen if it satisfies the placement constraint that the new stack must be adjacent to another stack to its left. If the chosen position does not satisfy it, the position at the other end of the segment is chosen. If neither of these two positions satisfies the placement constraint, the item is moved vertically until a position in which it touches a stack to its left is found.

Step 5. Adding items to complete the stack

Once the item at the base of the stack has been chosen, the item list is searched to find other items that can be placed in this stack, that is, items with the same base dimensions, the same supplier and supplier dock, and the same stackability code. All items in the stack must have the orientation selected for the item at the base of the stack.

Besides the individual conditions that each item must meet to be part of the stack, there are other joint constraints. For each item i in the stack, the number of items in the stack must not exceed ISM_i , a maximum stackability parameter. The density of the stack cannot exceed the maximum stack density defined for the truck in which the stack is loaded.

The total weight of the packed items in the stack above the bottom item cannot exceed $TMM_t\gamma$, where γ is the type of the bottom item. In order to satisfy this constraint, if there are other items that can be

part of the stack with a $TMM_t\gamma$ greater than that of the bottom item, the items can be swapped to have a bottom item with the largest $TMM_t\gamma$ and then allow more items to be stacked on top of it.

Items are piled up in the stack as long as the height of the stack does not exceed the truck height. When adding an item to the stack will not allow any other item to be included, we search the list and choose the item that can be placed in the stack and minimizes the empty space left between the stack and the roof of the truck.

Step 6. Checking the constraints limiting the weight on the axles

The process of adding stacks to the truck stops in three cases: when all items from a supplier have been loaded and the item list continues with those from another supplier; when all items on the list have been packed; or when no more items fit in the truck. If none of these conditions is met, the algorithm returns to Step 1.

Otherwise, the weights on the middle and rear axles must be calculated to ensure that they do not exceed their limits. If they do not, the packing is feasible. In the first case, the process goes to Step 1 to pack the items from the next supplier. In the second case, the algorithm stops, because an optimal packing has been found. In the third case, a complete feasible solution has been built and, if necessary, the best known solution for the truck is updated. If the packing does not satisfy the axle weight constraints, the solution is discarded and a new iteration is started.

Figure 4: Packing with stacks in the middle of the truck

7.2 Randomization strategies

Two types of randomization strategies have been added to the algorithm. Some of them are generic, to obtain diverse solutions, and others are specific, to force the solutions to satisfy the axle weight constraints and to pack the mandatory items.

The generic randomization strategy is applied at Step 1. In each iteration, a criterion is chosen to order the items: volume, weight, width, inventory cost. To introduce variability, the value of each item in the chosen criterion is perturbed by adding uniform random noise in the range $\pm 20\%$ of its original value. These perturbed values are used to sort the items, ensuring a different order each time the criterion is applied.

When a solution does not satisfy the axle weight constraints, in subsequent iterations we consider the possibility of not filling the truck width with two or more stacks but placing a single stack in the middle. Figure 4 illustrates this strategy, showing how the stacks can be positioned in the center of the truck to better distribute the weight on the axles. This is done probabilistically at Step 4 of the constructive algorithm. When selecting the position of the item, a middle position is chosen with a given probability P_{middle} , and if this is the case, the segment will not accommodate any additional stacks. This probability is initially 0, and each time the solution fails to satisfy the axle weight constraints, it is increased by 0.1. Conversely, if a solution is found that satisfies the constraints, the probability decreases by 0.1. This strategy is only used for stacks being placed from the cabin to the middle axle, because the constraint on this axle is more strict and difficult to satisfy than that on the rear axle.

If placing stacks in the middle is not enough to satisfy the axle weight constraints, even when $P_{middle} = 1$ and all stacks from the cabin to the middle axle are placed in the center, a further strategy consists of not completing the stacks up to the height of the truck in Step 5 of the constructive algorithm, but leaving them uncompleted. The maximum height that a stack can reach above the bottom item is given by $H_{truck}(1 - \alpha(x_{middle} - x)/x_{middle})$, where x is the stack position, x_{middle} the middle axle position, and α is initially set to 0 and increased by 0.1 with each iteration in which a feasible solution is not found and

decreased otherwise. As in the previous strategy, it is only applied to stacks from the cabin to the middle axle.

When the list of items contains some items marked as mandatory, packing all these items is more important than maximizing the volume packed. Therefore, a solution is considered better if it contains more mandatory items. Another randomization strategy tries to force their packing. When the algorithm has reached half of the allowed number of iterations, we check whether the best solution found contains all mandatory items. If it does, the procedure continues normally. Otherwise, to force the mandatory items to be considered for packing even though they belong to suppliers that are not at the top of the list, in subsequent iterations the non-mandatory items in the list can be skipped with a given probability. As in the previous strategies, this probability is initially 0 and increases until a solution is reached with all mandatory items packed, provided they all fit into the truck, and from then on it decreases. If not all mandatory items fit into the truck and another truck is needed to pack them, the procedure reverts to the initial objective of maximizing the volume of items packed.

8 Matheuristic strategies for solving the original problem

In this section, we discuss different ways of combining the two main components described in the previous sections into a matheuristic algorithm for solving the problem. Two issues have to be taken into account. First, the instances to be solved can be very large. Even after the decomposition procedures there may be very large components to be solved and the running time is limited. Therefore, to ensure that the integer linear model of the first phase always produces a truck and item assignment, several reduction techniques are applied. First, we apply a day-based filtering mechanism that restricts the items considered for each truck to those whose latest arrival time is close to the truck's arrival time, significantly reducing the number of decision variables. Second, we impose strict time limits on the solution of each integer linear model to avoid excessive computation on individual subproblems. Third, we set optimality gap tolerances that allow the solver to finish with high-quality solutions without requiring proof of optimality.

A second feature of our approach is that the integer linear model for assigning items to trucks is just an approximation, since the constraints related to the position of the items inside the trucks are not included. Each matheuristic strategy must define a way of solving the integer linear model, possibly including further reductions and relaxations, and a way of using the information derived from the solution of the model to proceed to the packing phase.

8.1 A simple iterative procedure: solving residual problems

A first strategy consists in iteratively solving the problem with the items still unpacked. This scheme is especially suited to small subproblems and works as follows:

Step 1. Solve the integer linear model defined by the items and trucks in the subproblem, as described in Section 6. The solution will consist of a set of trucks and their corresponding sets of assigned items.

Step 2. For each truck in the solution of the model, an attempt is made to pack all items assigned to it by applying the heuristic packing algorithm described in Section 7. If there are items that cannot be packed, put them in a list of unpacked items.

Step 3. If the list of unpacked items is empty, a feasible solution has been obtained and the algorithm stops. Otherwise, a new model, the residual model, is defined with the unpacked items and the planned and extra trucks that still have capacity left or have not been used in the solution of the previous models.

Step 4. Solve the residual model and return to Step 2.

In this first strategy the integer linear model is solved and the information about the trucks used and the items assigned to each truck is sent directly to the packing algorithm. The same idea of iteratively solving residual problems can be applied to larger subproblems by modifying the algorithm as follows:

Step 1. Solve the integer linear model defined by the items and trucks of the subproblem, as described in Section 6, but considering the z variables, corresponding to trucks, as binary, and the x variables, corresponding to items, as continuous. From the solution, we keep the set of trucks used, those for which the z variables take value 1.

Step 2. Consider a single list of all unpacked items (in the first iteration, the complete list of items). For each truck in the solution of the model, ordered by non-increasing arrival date, identify the sublist of

items that can be packed in the truck. Send the truck and its corresponding sublist of items to the packing algorithm. The packed items are removed from the list.

Step 3. If the list of items is not empty, a new model, the residual model, is defined with these items and the planned and extra trucks that still have capacity or have not been used in the solution of the previous models. Otherwise, a feasible solution has been obtained.

Step 4. Solve the residual model with the z variables as binary and the x variables as continuous, and return to Step 2.

In this second alternative, the model is partially relaxed and only the information about the trucks used is taken into account in the packing phase.

8.2 A Relax-and-Fix approach

A second strategy for combining the integer model for assigning items to trucks with the heuristic packing algorithm is the Relax-and-Fix framework. This is an iterative procedure in which, at each iteration, the variables of the integer linear model are divided into three groups. Some of them are kept as binary and integer, others are relaxed to be continuous, and some of those that were binary and integer in the previous iteration are fixed to their values in the previous solution. On the one hand, the size of the model is progressively decreased by fixing variables. On the other hand, at each iteration only a subset of variables are binary or integer, so the model is much easier to solve than the original problem, making it possible to apply it to large subproblems.

The Relax-and-Fix framework and its variants, Insert-and-Fix and Fractional-Relax-and-Fix, have been successfully applied to hard combinatorial problems, such as lot sizing and scheduling (Guimarães et al., 2013), bin packing (Paquay et al., 2018), routing (Ribeiro et al., 2019), or maritime problems (Friske et al., 2022). Adapting this general scheme to our specific problem involves deciding which subset of variables to keep as integer or binary, which part of the solution of the model to apply the packing algorithm to, and which part of the solution to fix at each iteration.

In our case, we follow a rolling horizon approach. Starting from the end of the planning horizon and moving towards the beginning, we select an interval of delivery days to keep the x variables as integer, and another interval, usually larger, to keep the z variables as binary. The model is solved and part of its integer solution, corresponding to an interval of several days, in which some trucks are used and some items assigned to them, is sent to the packing algorithm. The variables corresponding to the trucks used and the items packed into them are fixed from now on and the intervals shifted backwards.

The outline of the algorithm is as follows:

Step 1. Initialization

Set $T = H_e$, starting at the end of the planning horizon.

Set $w_x = k_1$ and $w_z = k_2$, the widths of the intervals in which x variables are kept as integers and z variables as binary.

Set $d_p = k_3$ the number of days to be packed in each iteration.

Step 2. Build a mixed integer linear problem

Among the variables not yet fixed, keep the x variables in the interval $(T - w_x + 1, T)$ as integer and the z variables in the interval $(T - w_z + 1, T)$ as binary. The remaining variables are relaxed to be continuous. If there are x variables that were integer in previous iterations and have not yet been fixed, they are kept as integer.

Step 3. Solve the mixed integer linear model

Step 4. Pack part of the solution of the model

Take each truck t whose arrival date TDA_t falls in the interval $(T - d_p + 1, T)$ in non-increasing order of arrival date. Send the truck to the packing algorithm with the list of items assigned to it in the solution of the model. If there are items assigned to a previous truck that were not packed and they can be packed into the current truck, they are also included in the list.

Step 5. Fix variables

The z variables corresponding to the trucks involved in Step 4, as well as the x variables corresponding to items packed into these trucks by the packing algorithm, are fixed for all subsequent iterations.

Step 6. Shift the intervals backwards

Set $T = T - d_p$ and go to Step 2.

The intervals move backwards in order to pack the items as late as possible so that inventory costs are minimized. Besides this design decision, the procedure relies on three parameters, k_1 , k_2 , and k_3 . The width of the x and z intervals might be equal, but there are major differences between these two types of variables. On the one hand, there are many more x than z variables. On the other hand, z variables have a more direct impact on the objective function. Therefore, the interval for the z variables can be larger, that is, $k_1 < k_2$. Concerning k_3 , there is a tradeoff. A small k_3 , packing a few days at each iteration, gives more flexibility to the process, at the expense of increasing the number of iterations. A large k_3 reduces the number of iterations, speeding up the process, but k_3 must always be lower than or equal to k_1 , to send part of the integer solution of the model to the packing algorithm.

The Relax-and-Fix algorithm described above is run several times until the time limit is reached. Each time it is run, its parameters k_1 , k_2 , change to obtain different solutions. Typically, they start by taking small values and then increase progressively.

A variant of this Relax-and-Fix strategy changes the list of items sent to the packing algorithm along with each truck in Step 4. Instead of sending the list of items assigned to this truck by the solution of the mixed integer linear model, a single common list of all items taking integer values in the solution is used for all trucks, ordered by non-increasing latest delivery date. For each particular truck, the list is filtered, keeping only items that can be packed into it. After applying the packing algorithm to each truck, the packed items are removed from the single list.

In our implementation, the first time the algorithm is run, $k_1 = 0$, so all x variables are relaxed to be continuous. In this case, the common item list contains all the items assigned to the trucks used with a value above a threshold. This threshold is set to 0.02 and $k_2 = k_3 = 1$. At each successive run, the intervals are increased by one unit.

8.3 A floating strategy

The two matheuristic approaches discussed above fix all or some of the item-truck assignments of the packing phase at each iteration. New models are then solved in subsequent iterations, but without the possibility of changing the fixed assignments of previous iterations. The third strategy we have developed is more flexible and none of the item-truck assignment is fixed until a complete feasible solution has been found. The algorithm scheme is:

Step 1. Solve the integer linear model defined by the items and trucks of the subproblem, as described in Section 6, but keeping the z_t variables as binary and relaxing the x_{it} variables to be continuous.

Step 2. Take the list of trucks used in the solution ($z_t = 1$) and the list of all items, sorted by non-increasing early delivery date.

Step 3. Send each of the trucks used to the packing algorithm in non-increasing order of arrival date. For each truck, its item list will include all items not yet packed that can be loaded into the truck according to their product type and delivery dates.

Step 4. If all items have been packed, STOP. A feasible solution has been found. Otherwise, go to step 5.

Step 5. Build a modified model. For all the trucks used, their variables z_t are fixed at 1. If a truck has not been able to pack all the items in its item list, its capacity in volume or weight is reduced to the value reached by the packing algorithm, choosing the criterion that has attained its limit. None of the x_{it} variables, corresponding to the items packed in each truck, is fixed. If none of the truck capacities is reduced, a constraint on the number of trucks to be used is added, to prevent the procedure from cycling. In this constraint, the number of trucks not yet used that could accommodate some of the unpacked items is made greater than or equal to 1. Go back to step 1.

An even more flexible strategy does not fix the variables corresponding to the trucks used in step 5, but only reduces the limits of those that could not pack all the items in their item list, then leaving to the model the possibility of choosing a different set of trucks in the next iteration.

8.4 Embedding the strategies in an iterative procedure

The challenge rules set a time limit for each instance, 3600 seconds in most cases and 1800 in some others. The strategies described require a running time that depends on the number of subproblems and the size of the largest subproblems. As these vary greatly between instances, the time required to go through each

procedure and obtain a feasible solution also varies. To efficiently use the available computational time, the algorithm employs an adaptive parameter adjustment strategy. This iterative procedure:

- Expands the day filter for item-truck compatibility until all items that can be loaded into each truck are considered
- Reduces the optimality gap tolerance in the integer linear programming models to improve solution quality
- Increases the number of packing algorithm iterations
- In the Relax-and-Fix framework, progressively enlarges the time intervals (k_1, k_2, k_3) to improve the exploration of the solution space

This approach ensures that longer available time translates into more thorough optimization while maintaining the algorithm’s efficiency for instances with tighter time limits.

8.5 Post-optimization improvement: Local search for inventory cost reduction

The packing algorithm seeks to maximize the volume of the items loaded into a truck. This objective sometimes conflicts with minimizing inventory costs. To reduce the inventory costs without increasing the transportation cost, we have developed a post-optimization local search procedure.

The local search examines pairs of trucks arriving on different days to identify beneficial item exchanges:

Step 1. Truck pair identification.

For each pair of trucks (t_1, t_2) with arrival dates $d_1 < d_2$, determine whether there are items in t_1 that could be loaded in t_2 and items in t_2 that can go in t_1 .

Step 2. Three-phase exchange process.

1. Empty both trucks
2. Reload the later-arriving truck (t_2), prioritizing items with highest inventory costs per day
3. Attempt to pack all remaining items in the earlier truck (t_1)

Step 3. Solution acceptance.

Accept the exchange if all items can be successfully packed and the inventory cost is reduced.

This post-optimization step integrates seamlessly with all matheuristic strategies described in Sections 8.1-8.3. It is applied after obtaining a complete solution for each subproblem, adding minimal computational overhead.

9 Computational study

The computational study has three main objectives: first, to identify which of the six strategies described in Section 8 is best suited to the characteristics of the problem. Second, to compare the results of our best strategy with the best results reported under the challenge conditions, and third to study whether the solutions improve when the algorithm is run for longer times.

9.1 Identifying the best matheuristic strategy

The six strategies described in Section 8 were coded in C++ and the mixed integer linear models were solved using CPLEX version 22.1.1.0. The 155 instances of sets C and X were solved on a Linux OS machine (Linux version 3.10.0-693.5.2.el7.x86-64, gcc version 4.8.5 20150623, Red Hat 4.8.5-16 (GCC), with 4 CPU, 8 Threads, 2.40 GHz, and 4 GB of RAM) with running times adjusted to be similar to the challenge conditions, in which most instances had a time limit of 3600 seconds while some had only 1800 seconds.

For reference, the official challenge environment consisted of programs running on Google Cloud Platform virtual machines with 8 CPU, 32 GB of RAM and CentOS 7. While our testing environment had more limited computational resources, the time limits were calibrated to ensure comparable algorithmic performance evaluation.

The first six rows of Table 3 compare the results obtained by each strategy with the minimum value of all of them, in terms of the number of instances in which the minimum is reached, and the average and

the maximum percentage deviation from this minimum. It can be seen that the strategies based on solving residual problems do not work well. They seem to be too rigid, leaving unpacked items scattered over the planning horizon at each iteration. To pack these items in subsequent iterations would require more trucks that would not be fully used.

Strategies using the Relax & Fix framework are much better. Starting from the end of the planning horizon and going backward seems to be well suited to the objective of the problem. Nevertheless, there is a clear difference between the two strategies developed, and the use of a single list of items instead of the item assignment given by the model is clearly the better. The Floating strategies work quite well, although not as well as the Relax & Fix. Of the two of them, fixing the truck variables at each iteration appears to be better than leaving everything unfixed, possibly because in the latter case the link between successive iterations is partially lost and progress towards a good solution is not ensured.

According to the results in the table, we could have chosen the Relax & Fix strategy with the single list of items as our best. However, a detailed analysis of the results showed that the Floating strategy, in which the z variables are fixed along the iterations but not the x variables, was somewhat complementary, obtaining a good solution when the other could not, and the other way round. Therefore, we tried a hybrid strategy, starting with Relax & Fix and switching to Floating after reaching half the time or a given number of iterations. The results of this hybrid strategy appear in the last row of the table, showing a clear advantage over all the individual strategies.

Table 3: Comparing the six proposed strategies

Strategy	# Minimum	% Average deviation	% Maximum deviation
Residual 1 (z binary, x integer)	7	2.41	21.46
Residual 2 (z binary, x continuous)	2	2.35	17.05
Relax & Fix 1 (item assigned by model)	23	0.71	2.80
Relax & Fix 2 (single list of items)	91	0.16	2.17
Floating 1 (not fixing item assignments)	40	0.29	2.45
Floating 2 (not fixing z and x variables)	7	1.09	4.56
Hybrid Relax & Fix and Floating	122	-0.16	2.52

9.2 Comparing with the best results in the Renault Challenge

The ROADEF-RENAULT challenge was won by Florian Fontan and Luc Libralesso from France, who achieved the best overall results and 84 minimum solutions out of 155 instances. In a close second place came the Chinese team of Wangqi Xiong, Xinhang Zhang, Lingxiao Chen, Jiajin Hu, and Xuan Liu. In third place, the ORTEC company team, Ruggiero Seccia, Annelieke Baller, Gesche Dithmer, Ilya Artsyman, Jacob Kooijman, Lotte Berghman, Wouter Kool, and Wouter Merx. The results they obtained for each instance in sets C and X were published on the challenge website, so a direct comparison is possible. It is also possible to compare with the results reported by Jakob Schulte and Daniel Wetzels, whose study has recently been published (Schulte and Wetzels, 2025).

Our hybrid algorithm was run on a machine identical to the one used in the challenge, to allow a direct comparison. In Table 4 the five proposals are compared in respect of the minimum they obtained in each instance, in terms of the number of minima and the average and maximum deviation from the minimum.

It can be observed that our hybrid algorithm attains a high number of minimum solutions, but more importantly, its average and maximum deviations from the minimum are very low, so that even for the instances in which it does not reach the minimum, a high-quality solution is obtained. If we compare our results with the minimum values reported for the final phase of the challenge, and including the improvements reported by Schulte & Wetzels, we have obtained 75 new best solutions, with an average improvement of 0.26 % over the 155 instances of sets C and X. Our code as well as the solutions obtained are available at <https://github.com/FranciscoParrenoTorres/Roadef2022>.

Table 4: Comparing algorithms in the conditions of the challenge

Team	# Minimum	% Average deviation	% Maximum deviation
Fontan & Libralesso	47	2.91	26.04
Xiong et al.	18	2.77	26.43
Seccia et al.	11	6.28	32.07
Schulte & Wetzel	17	5.91	28.78
Our hybrid algorithm	79	0.28	1.88

9.3 Running the algorithm with longer execution times

The planning horizon for this problem is around 8 weeks. Hence, it might make sense to extend the running times beyond 3600 seconds if the algorithms were able to improve their solutions. The challenge organisers gave all participating teams the opportunity of running their algorithms without time limit and reporting their results. Several teams that had participated in the challenge ran their algorithms for times of up to 16 hours and submitted new results. These results are published on the challenge website. For 126 out of 155 instances, all but the smallest, new best solutions have been found, showing that the algorithms were able to use longer running time to explore the solution space more deeply and obtain better solutions. The current set of best solutions can be considered as a set of extremely good solutions obtained by the common effort of several of the best competitors in the challenge.

In order to compare with the best known results and assess whether our algorithm was able to improve the solutions when running for longer times, we ran it for times equivalent to four hours and eight hours of the machine used in the challenge. The results appear in Table 5.

Table 5: Running our algorithm for longer computing times

% Improvement	$\leq 60m.$	4 hours	8 hours
Minimum	-3.87	-3.35	-3.27
Maximum	2.61	2.59	2.58
Average	-0.61	-0.40	-0.36
Best	33	47	47
New best	30	43	43

It can be observed that when run under the challenge time limits (1800-3600 seconds) our algorithm was able to obtain 30 new best solutions and 3 matches with the best known solution, with an average distance to the best solution of 0.61 % and a maximum distance of 3.87 %. When run for 4 hours, the results improved in 124 instances over those obtained with the challenge time limits, obtaining 43 new best solutions, the 30 obtained when running for 1 hour plus 13 additional ones, and reducing the average distance to the best solution to 0.40 % and the maximum distance to 3.35 %. When run for 8 hours, the results improved in 87 instances over those obtained in 4 hours, but very slightly, reducing the average distance to 0.36 % and the maximum distance to 3.27 %, but finding only 2 new best solutions, although due to the random elements of the algorithm, 2 new best solutions previously found could not be reached. Overall, if we take the best solutions obtained in the three runs, 45 new best solutions were found, with an average distance of 0.32 % and a maximum distance of 3.27 % to the best known solutions.

9.4 Analyzing the variability of the algorithm

The proposed algorithm has some randomization procedures in the packing phase, so a question raised in the previous section that has to be answered is to what extent the solutions vary over independent executions of the algorithm. In order to assess the variability of the solutions, we have run the algorithm 4 and 8 times with different seeds with a time limit equivalent to one hour on the machine of the challenge.

The average percentage difference between the maximum and minimum values of the solutions obtained in 4 independent executions was 0.26 %. The maximum was 2.64 % but only in 4 instances out of 155 the

deviation exceeded 1 % and only once exceeded 2 %. When the algorithm was run 8 times, the average percentage difference was 0.34 %. Again, the maximum was 2.64 % and again it was the only case that exceeded 2 %, with three more cases exceeding 1 %. The algorithm appears to be quite stable, with very small differences in the values obtained in repeated independent runs.

10 Conclusions

This paper addresses the complex part transportation problem from suppliers to factories in the automotive industry, as proposed in the 2022 ROADEF-Renault challenge. We have developed a solution procedure that obtains very good results under the conditions of the challenge as well as for longer run times.

First, we have developed effective decomposition strategies that reduce large-scale instances to more manageable components based on truck routes, product types, and delivery time windows. For each component, the structure of the problem naturally leads to dividing it into an assignment phase and a packing phase. For the assignment phase we have proposed an integer linear model and for the packing phase, a metaheuristic algorithm handling all practical constraints, such as weight distribution, stability, orientation, fragility, and multidrop requirements.

Then we have designed several matheuristic frameworks combining assignment and packing phases, with our hybrid Relax-and-Fix and Floating strategy proving most effective. The proposed hybrid algorithm demonstrates robust performance across diverse instance characteristics, from small subproblems with hundreds of items to large-scale instances with tens of thousands of parts. Under the challenge conditions, 75 new best solutions are found out of 155 instances, and 43 when comparing with the best reported results for longer running times.

This work can be extended in two ways. On the one hand, the elements of the problem could be refined, with an integer linear model for the assignment phase closer to the real problem being modeled and a better packing algorithm. On the other hand, the solution procedures developed here could be applied to other complex logistic applications with a similar assignment-packing structure.

Our results demonstrate that sophisticated matheuristic approaches can yield substantial improvements in large-scale industrial logistics problem by exploiting and combining the power of pure mathematical programming and metaheuristic methods.

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References

- Allen, S., Burke, E., Kendall, G., 2011. A hybrid placement strategy for the three-dimensional strip packing problem. *European Journal of Operational Research* 209, 219–227. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221710006211>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2010.09.023>.
- Alonso, M., Alvarez-Valdes, R., Iori, M., Parreño, F., Tamarit, J., 2017. Mathematical models for multicontainer loading problems. *Omega* 66, 106–117. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305048316000335>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2016.02.002>.
- Alonso, M., Martinez-Sykora, A., Alvarez-Valdes, R., Parreño, F., 2022. The pallet-loading vehicle routing problem with stability constraints. *European Journal of Operational Research* 302, 860–873. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2022.01.035>.
- Alonso, M.T., Alvarez-Valdes, R., Iori, M., Parreño, F., 2019. Mathematical models for Multi Container Loading Problems with practical constraints. *Computers and Industrial Engineering* 127, 722–733. doi:10.1016/j.cie.2018.11.012.

- Alonso, M.T., Alvarez-Valdes, R., Tamarit, J.M., Parreño, F., 2014. A reactive GRASP algorithm for the container loading problem with load-bearing constraints. *European Journal of Industrial Engineering* 8, 669–694. URL: <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/EJIE.2014.065734>, doi:10.1504/EJIE.2014.065734.
- Alvarez, A., Munari, P., Morabito, R., 2018. Iterated local search and simulated annealing algorithms for the inventory routing problem. *International Transactions in Operational Research* 25, 1785–1809. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/itor.12547>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/itor.12547>.
- Alvarez, D., Alvarez-Valdes, R., Parreño, F., 2015. A GRASP algorithm for the container loading problem with multidrop constraints. *Pesquisa Operacional* 35, 1–24. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/0101-7438.2015.035.01.0001>.
- Archetti, C., Bianchessi, N., Irnich, S., Speranza, M.G., 2014. Formulations for an inventory routing problem. *International Transactions in Operational Research* 21, 353–374. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/itor.12076>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/itor.12076>.
- Archetti, C., Guastaroba, G., Huerta-Muñoz, D.L., Speranza, M.G., 2021. A kernel search heuristic for the multivehicle inventory routing problem. *International Transactions in Operational Research* 28, 2984–3013. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/itor.12945>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/itor.12945>.
- Avella, P., Boccia, M., Wolsey, L.A., 2018. Single-period cutting planes for inventory routing problems. *Transportation Science* 52, 497–508. doi:10.1287/trsc.2016.0729.
- Bertazzi, L., Speranza, M.G., 2013. Inventory routing problems with multiple customers. *EURO Journal on Transportation and Logistics* 2, 255–275. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2192437620301199>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13676-013-0027-z>.
- Bischoff, E., Ratcliff, M., 1995. Issues in the development of approaches to container loading. *Omega* 23, 377–390. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/030504839500015G>, doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-0483\(95\)00015-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-0483(95)00015-G).
- Bonet Filella, G., Trivella, A., Corman, F., 2023. Modeling soft unloading constraints in the multi-drop container loading problem. *European Journal of Operational Research* 308, 336–352. doi:10.1016/J.EJOR.2022.10.033.
- Bortfeldt, A., Wäscher, G., 2013. Constraints in container loading – a state-of-the-art review. *European Journal of Operational Research* 229, 1–20. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S037722171200937X>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2012.12.006>.
- Braga, N., Alves, C., Macedo, R., Carvalho, J.V.D., 2016. Combined cutting stock and scheduling: a matheuristic approach. *International Journal of Innovative Computing and Applications* 7, 135–146. URL: <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/IJICA.2016.078724>, doi:10.1504/IJICA.2016.078724.
- Çalk, H., Juwet, M., Yaman, H., Vanden Berghe, G., 2023. Cargo securing under multi-drop and axle weight constraints. *European Journal of Operational Research* 307, 157–176. doi:10.1016/J.EJOR.2022.08.031.
- Cildoz, M., Mateo, P.M., Alonso, M.T., Parreño, F., Alvarez-Valdes, R., Mallor, F., 2024. The optimal container selection problem for parts transportation in the automotive sector. *Expert Systems with Applications* 247, 123321. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.123321>.
- Correcher, J., Alonso, M., Parreño, F., Alvarez-Valdes, R., 2017. Solving a large multicontainer loading problem in the car manufacturing industry. *Computers Operations Research* 82, 139–152. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305054817300126>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2017.01.012>.

- de Queiroz, T.A., Miyazawa, F.K., 2013. Two-dimensional strip packing problem with load balancing, load bearing and multi-drop constraints. *International Journal of Production Economics* 145, 511–530. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2013.04.032>.
- Fanslau, T., Bortfeldt, A., 2010. A tree search algorithm for solving the container loading problem. *INFORMS Journal on Computing* 22, 222–235. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1287/ijoc.1090.0338>.
- Friske, M.W., Buriol, L.S., Camponogara, E., 2022. A Relax-and-Fix and Fix-and-Optimize algorithm for a maritime inventory routing problem. *Computers Operations Research* 137, 105520. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305054821002604>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2021.105520>.
- Fuellerer, G., Doerner, K.F., Hartl, R.F., Iori, M., 2010. Metaheuristics for vehicle routing problems with three-dimensional loading constraints. *European Journal of Operational Research* 201, 751–759. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221709002252>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2009.03.046>.
- Guimarães, L., Klabjan, D., Almada-Lobo, B., 2013. Pricing, relaxing and fixing under lot sizing and scheduling. *European Journal of Operational Research* 230, 399–411. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221713003445>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2013.04.030>.
- Iori, M., Locatelli, M., Moreira, M.C.O., Silveira, T., 2020. Reactive GRASP-based algorithm for pallet building problem with visibility and contiguity constraints, in: *Proceedings of the international conference on computational logistics*, Springer. p. 651–665. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-59747-4_42.
- Junqueira, L., Morabito, R., Sato Yamashita, D., 2012a. Three-dimensional container loading models with cargo stability and load bearing constraints. *Computers Operations Research* 39, 74–85. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305054810001486>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2010.07.017>. special Issue on Knapsack Problems and Applications.
- Junqueira, L., Morabito, R., Sato Yamashita, D., 2012b. MIP-based approaches for the container loading problem with multi-drop constraints. *Annals of Operations Research* 199, 51–75. doi:[10.1007/S10479-011-0942-Z](https://doi.org/10.1007/S10479-011-0942-Z).
- Knoll, D., Neumeier, D., Prügmeier, M., Reinhart, G., 2019. An automated packaging planning approach using machine learning. *Procedia CIRP* 81, 576–581. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2019.03.158>.
- Kurpel, D.V., Scarpin, C.T., Pécora Junior, J.E., Schenekemberg, C.M., Coelho, L.C., 2020. The exact solutions of several types of container loading problems. *European Journal of Operational Research* 284, 87–107. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221719310136>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2019.12.012>.
- Lim, A., Ma, H., Qiu, C., Zhu, W., 2013. The single container loading problem with axle weight constraints. *International Journal of Production Economics* 144, 358–369. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925527313001084>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2013.03.001>.
- Neuenfeldt Júnior, A., Silva, E., Francescatto, M., Rosa, C.B., Siluk, J., 2022. The rectangular two-dimensional strip packing problem real-life practical constraints: A bibliometric overview. *Computers Operations Research* 137, 105521. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305054821002616>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2021.105521>.
- Nguyen, A., Khatouf, M., Serrano, C., 2022. Challenge EURO/ROADEF 2022: Truck loading. https://github.com/renault-iaa/challenge-roadef-2022/blob/main/challenge_ROADEF_2022.pdf. Accessed on 2024-09-18.
- Nieuwenhuis, P., Beresford, A., Choi, A.K.Y., 2012. Shipping or local production? CO2 impact of a strategic decision: An automotive industry case study. *International Journal of Production Economics* 140, 138–148. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2012.01.034>.

- Paquay, C., Limbourg, S., Schyns, M., 2018. A tailored two-phase constructive heuristic for the three-dimensional multiple bin size bin packing problem with transportation constraints. *European Journal of Operational Research* 267, 52–64. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221717310214>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2017.11.010>.
- Pollaris, H., Braekers, K., Caris, A., Janssens, G.K., Limbourg, S., 2015. Vehicle routing problems with loading constraints: state-of-the-art and future directions. *OR Spectrum* 37, 297–330. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00291-014-0386-3>.
- Pollaris, H., Braekers, K., Caris, A., Janssens, G.K., Limbourg, S., 2016. Capacitated vehicle routing problem with sequence-based pallet loading and axle weight constraints. *EURO Journal on Transportation and Logistics* 5, 231–255. doi:[10.1007/s13676-014-0064-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13676-014-0064-2).
- Polyakovskiy, S., M’Hallah, R., 2018. A hybrid feasibility constraints-guided search to the two-dimensional bin packing problem with due dates. *European Journal of Operational Research* 266, 819–839. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221717309591>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2017.10.046>.
- Ramos, A., Oliveira, J., Gonçalves, J., Lopes, M., 2016. A container loading algorithm with static mechanical equilibrium stability constraints. *Transportation Research, Part B* 91, 565–581. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trb.2016.06.003>.
- Ramos, A.G., Oliveira, J.F., Gonçalves, J.F., Lopes, M.P., 2015. Dynamic stability metrics for the container loading problem. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 60, 480–497. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0968090X15003459>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2015.09.012>.
- Ramos, A.G., Silva, E., Oliveira, J., 2018. A new load balance methodology for container loading problem in road transportation. *European Journal of Operational Research* 266, 1140–1152. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2017.10.050>.
- Ribeiro, C.C., Santos, T.d.A., de Souza, C.C., 2019. Multicast routing under quality of service constraints for vehicular ad hoc networks: mathematical formulation and a relax-and-fix heuristic. *International Transactions in Operational Research* 26, 1339–1364. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/itor.12605>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/itor.12605>.
- Schulte, J., Wetzels, D., 2025. Two-phase matheuristic for assignment and truck loading problems. *European Journal of Operational Research* 322, 105–120. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2024.10.020>.
- Sharir, M., 1981. A strong-connectivity algorithm and its applications in data flow analysis. *Computers Mathematics with Applications* 7, 67–72. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0898122181900080>, doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0898-1221\(81\)90008-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0898-1221(81)90008-0).
- Siems, E., Land, A., Seuring, S., 2021. Dynamic capabilities in sustainable supply chain management: An inter-temporal comparison of the food and automotive industries. *International Journal of Production Economics* 236, 108128.
- Stone, T., 2024. New advances in weight-in-motion direct enforcement. <https://www.traffictotechnologytoday.com/news/weighing-systems/feature-new-advances-in-wim-direct-enforcement.html>. Accessed on 2024-09-26.
- Toffolo, T.A., Esprit, E., Wauters, T., Vanden Berghe, G., 2017. A two-dimensional heuristic decomposition approach to a three-dimensional multiple container loading problem. *European Journal of Operational Research* 257, 526–538. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221716305707>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2016.07.033>.
- Wei, L., Oon, W.C., Zhu, W., Lim, A., 2011. A skyline heuristic for the 2d rectangular packing and strip packing problems. *European Journal of Operational Research* 215, 337–346. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221711005510>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2011.06.022>.